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PROGRAMME
DE RECHERCHE
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Experimental Study on Stabilisation of High-Pressure CO₂-diluted Swirled CH₄-Oxyflames in a Coaxial Burner

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Transforming industry through Carbon Capture for Utilisation & Storage (CCUS)

Global direct CO₂ emissions by sector in 2017 [1]

Emissions reductions for cement, iron and steel, and chemicals industries following the Clean Technology Scenario [1]

Post-Combustion CO₂ recovery

Oxy-combustion HP

State of the art for experimental studies

- Non-premixed swirling gaseous-fuel flames with an oxygen-enriched oxidizer

Boushaki

Nemitallah, Habib,
Abubakar, Mokheimer

LUNDS
UNIVERSITET

Li et al. (2017)

Skryja et al. (2022)

Sautet, Honoré

Degenève et al. (2019)

- Partially premixed swirling oxyflames of methane at high pressure

Saanum et Ditaranto (2017)

No experimental study for Non-premixed Swirled Oxyflames at high pressure!

Context of the study

Objective

To investigate experimentally how flow parameters influence the topology and stability of pressurized methane oxyflames.

This work forms part of the **OXY3C project**, funded under the **SPLEEN** French research programme dedicated to the **decarbonisation of industrial processes**.

Summary

1. **Experimental Set-up:** OXYTEC HP Combustor.
2. **Flame imaging:** visual range and OH* chemiluminescence imaging.
3. **Flame stability limits:** identification of stable & unstable conditions for high-pressure oxyflames.

1. Experimental Set-up

Overview of the OXYTEC HP Combustor

- Built at **EM2C** laboratory.
- Can operate under:
 - **CO₂ & H₂O dilution.**
 - **4 bar of chamber pressure, independent of mass flow rates.**
 - Thermal power up to **$P_W=180\text{kW}$.**
 - **Premixed & non-premixed configuration.**

Picture of the OXYTEC HP Combustor (Credit to Pierre Fauré from EM2C lab).

Overview of the OXYTEC HP Combustor

- ① Injector
- ② Combustion chamber:
 - Dimensions 150 x 150 x 250 mm
 - 4 convenient optical windows
- ③ Exhaust pipe
- ④ Optical window
- ⑤ Convergent followed by a pressure control valve

Injector of the OXYTEC HP Combustor

The injector is composed of:

- A central pipe for **CH₄** injection
- An annular channel for **CO₂+O₂** injection

Momentum flux ratio: $J = \frac{\rho_{annular} u_{annular}^2}{\rho_{CH_4} u_{CH_4}^2}$

Global equivalence ratio: $\phi_g = 4 \frac{\dot{m}_{CH_4}}{\dot{m}_{O_2}}$

CO₂ molar fraction: $X_{CO_2} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{CO_2}}{\dot{Q}_{CO_2} + \dot{Q}_{O_2}}$

Injector of the OXYTEC HP Combustor

The annular channel is fed by:

- An **axial stream**
- An **azimuthal stream**

This permits to **control an annular swirl intensity**:

$$S_2 = S_2^{max} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\dot{m}_{AXI}}{\dot{m}_{AZI}}\right)^2}$$

Diagnostics used

- ① Visible range CMOS slow motion camera.
- ② Intensified CCD camera with 305 to 315nm band pass filter for chemiluminescence OH* for flame-front study.

3. Flame imaging

3.1 Effect of Pressure

3.2 Effect of annular Swirl intensity

3.3 Effect of Momentum flux ratio

3.4 Effect of CO₂ Dilution

Effect of Pressure

Visible range imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.95$
- $S_2 = 0.85$
- $J = 0.82$
- $X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
- $P_W = 21kW$
- Mass flow rates

P=1.2 bar

P=2.5 bar

P=4.0 bar

Slow motion movies at speed x0.16 in visible range.

- **Jet flames type.**
- **Soot-to-blue intensity ratio increases.**
Joo *et al.* [2]: reduced thermal diffusion thickness.

Effect of Pressure

Visible range imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.95$
- $S_2 = 0.85$
- $J = 0.82$
- $X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
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Slow motion movies at speed x0.16 in visible range.

○ Jet flames type

○ Soot-t
Joo et

➤ Higher pressure at constant mass flow rates increases soot production.

Effect of Pressure

OH* imaging

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- $J = 0.82$
- $X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
- $P_W = 21kW$
- Mass flow rates

P=1.2 bar

P=2.5 bar

P=4.0 bar

Normalized line-of-sight integrated OH average imaging, with Otsu white isocontour.*

- Flames are **not symmetrical**.
 - **Two distinct regions:**
 - **Zone 1:** unaffected by the pressure level.
 - **Zone 2:** the length of this diffuse flame front decreases.
- Xi et al. [3]: same observations.

Effect of Pressure

OH* imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.95$
- $S_2 = 0.85$
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- $X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
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- Flames are **not symmetrical**.

- Two distinct regions

- **Zone 1:** unaffected

- **Zone 2:** the length of this diffuse flame front decreases.

Xi et al. [3]: same observations.

➤ Higher pressure at constant mass flow rates decreases the flame-front length.

What happens if $U_{annular}$ is kept constant?

Effect of Pressure

OH* imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.94$
- $S_2 = 0.80$
- $J = 0.83$
- $X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
- $U_{annular}$

P = 1.5 bar

P = 2.0 bar

Normalized line-of-sight integrated OH average imaging, with Otsu white isocontour.*

- Flames seem to **have comparable** :
 - **Topology**
 - **Flame-front length**

Effect of Pressure

OH* imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.94$
- $S_2 = 0.80$
- $J = 0.83$
- $X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
- $U_{annular}$

P = 1.5 bar

P = 2.0 bar

Normalized line-of-sight integrated OH* average imaging, with Otsu white isocontour.

○ Flames seem to have comparable :

- Topology
- Flame-front length

➤ Higher pressure at constant exit velocities gives comparable flames.

WIP: need to test this at higher pressure

Effect of S2

Visible range imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.95$
- **P = 2.5 bar**
- J = 1.1
- $X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
- $P_W = 21kW$
- Mass flow rates

S2 = 0.55

S2 = 0.75

S2 = 0.95

S2 = 1.15

Slow motion movies at speed x0.16 in visible range.

- Soot-to-blue intensity ratio decreases.

Effect of S2

Visible range imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.95$
- **P = 2.5 bar**
- J = 1.1
- $X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
- $P_W = 21kW$
- Mass flow rates

S2 = 0.55

S2 = 0.75

S2 = 0.95

S2 = 1.15

Slow motion movies at speed x0.16 in visible range.

○ Soot-to-blue intensity

➤ Higher annular swirl decreases the flame soot luminosity.

Effect of S2

OH* imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.95$
- **P = 2.5 bar**
- $J = 1.1$
- $X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
- $P_W = 21kW$
- Mass flow rates

S2 = 0.55

S2 = 0.75

S2 = 0.95

S2 = 1.15

Normalized line-of-sight integrated OH* average imaging, with Otsu white isocontour.

- **Flames from jet type to V type.**
Degeneve *et al.* [4], Chen *et al.* [5]: formation of a central recirculation zone.
- **The length of the flame front decreases:** intensified turbulent mixing and shear level.

Strongly recirculating non-premixed flames [5]

Effect of S2

OH* imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.95$
- **P = 2.5 bar**
- $J = 1.1$
- $X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
- $P_W = 21kW$
- Mass flow rates

S2 = 0.55

S2 = 0.75

S2 = 0.95

S2 = 1.15

Normalized line-of-sight integrated OH* average imaging, with Otsu white isocontour.

- Flames from jet type to V type.

Degeneve et al. [4], Chen et al. [5]: formation of a central recirculation zone.

- The length of the flame and shear level.

➤ Higher annular swirl promotes the creation of a recirculation zone.

Strongly recirculating non-premixed flames [5]

Effect of J

OH* imaging

Constant parameters:

- $S2 = 0.85$
- $P = 1.2 \text{ bar}$
- $X_{CO2} = 0.60$
- $P_W = 21 \text{ kW}$
- Mass flow rates

Normalized line-of-sight integrated OH* average imaging, with Otsu white isocontour.

$$J = \frac{\rho_{\text{annular}} u_{\text{annular}}^2}{\rho_{CH4} u_{CH4}^2}$$

$$J = 0.82$$

$$\phi_g = 0.95$$

$$J = 0.91$$

$$\phi_g = 0.91$$

$$J = 1.06$$

$$\phi_g = 0.84$$

$$J = 1.18$$

$$\phi_g = 0.80$$

- o Flames from **jet type** to **V type**.

Degeneve *et al.* [4], Chen *et al.* [5]: formation of a central recirculation zone.

Effect of J

OH* imaging

Constant parameters:

- $S_2 = 0.85$
- $P = 1.2$ bar
- $X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
- $P_W = 21$ kW
- Mass flow rates

Normalized line-of-sight integrated OH* average imaging, with Otsu white isocontour.

$$J = \frac{\rho_{\text{annular}} u_{\text{annular}}^2}{\rho_{CH_4} u_{CH_4}^2}$$

$$J = 0.82$$

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$$J = 0.91$$

$$\phi_g = 0.91$$

$$J = 1.06$$

$$\phi_g = 0.84$$

$$J = 1.18$$

$$\phi_g = 0.80$$

○ Flames from
Degeneve et al.

➤ Higher momentum flux ratio promotes the creation of a recirculation zone.

Effect of CO₂ dilution

Visible range imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.95$
- **P = 4.0 bar**
- $S_2 = 1.05$
- $P_W = 21\text{kW}$
- Mass flow rates

$$X_{CO_2} = 0.60$$

$$J = 0.81$$

$$X_{CO_2} = 0.63$$

$$J = 0.95$$

$$X_{CO_2} = 0.65$$

$$J = 1.1$$

$$X_{CO_2} = 0.68$$

$$J = 1.3$$

Slow motion movies at speed x0.16 in visible range.

- Jet flame type.
- Soot-to-blue intensity ratio decreases.
Oh et Shin [6]:
 - **Thermal effect:** more mass flow of the oxidizer stream.
 - **Chemical effect:** CO₂ on soot formation.

Effect of CO₂ dilution

Visible range imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.95$
- **$P = 4.0$ bar**
- $S_2 = 1.05$
- $P_W = 21$ kW
- Mass flow rates

$X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
 $J = 0.81$

$X_{CO_2} = 0.63$
 $J = 0.95$

$X_{CO_2} = 0.65$
 $J = 1.1$

$X_{CO_2} = 0.68$
 $J = 1.3$

Slow motion movies at speed $\times 0.16$ in visible range.

○ Jet flame type.

○ Soot-to-blue intensity ratio
Oh et Shin [6]:

- Thermal effect: more mass flow of the oxidizer stream.
- Chemical effect: CO₂ on soot formation.

➤ Higher CO₂ dilution decreases soot production.

Effect of CO₂ dilution

OH* imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.95$
- **P = 4.0 bar**
- $S_2 = 1.05$
- $P_W = 21\text{kW}$
- Mass flow rates

Normalized line-of-sight integrated OH* average imaging, with 25% intensity white isocontour.

$X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
 $J = 0.81$

$X_{CO_2} = 0.63$
 $J = 0.95$

$X_{CO_2} = 0.65$
 $J = 1.1$

$X_{CO_2} = 0.68$
 $J = 1.3$

- **Two distinct regions** can be identified:
 - **Zone 1:** unaffected by CO₂ dilution level.
 - **Zone 2:** the length of this diffuse flame front increases.

Effect of CO2 dilution

OH* imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.95$
- **$P = 4.0$ bar**
- $S_2 = 1.05$
- $P_W = 21$ kW
- Mass flow rates

Normalized line-of-sight integrated OH* average imaging, with 25% intensity white isocontour.

$X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
 $J = 0.81$

$X_{CO_2} = 0.63$
 $J = 0.95$

$X_{CO_2} = 0.65$
 $J = 1.1$

$X_{CO_2} = 0.68$
 $J = 1.3$

- Two distinct regions
 - **Zone 1:** unaffected
 - **Zone 2:** the length

➤ Higher CO2 dilution increases the flame-front length.

Effect of CO2 dilution

OH* imaging

Constant parameters:

- $\phi_g = 0.95$
- **$P = 4.0$ bar**
- $S_2 = 1.05$
- $P_W = 21$ kW
- Mass flow rates

$X_{CO_2} = 0.60$
 $J = 0.81$

$X_{CO_2} = 0.63$
 $J = 0.95$

$X_{CO_2} = 0.65$
 $J = 1.1$

$X_{CO_2} = 0.68$
 $J = 1.3$

Dilution limit?

Normalized line-of-sight integrated OH* average imaging, with 25% intensity white isocontour.

- Two distinct regions
 - **Zone 1:** unaffected
 - **Zone 2:** the length

➤ Higher CO2 dilution increases the flame-front length.

4. Flame stability limits

CO₂ dilution limit

Flame stability limit with respect to CO₂ dilution improves with:

- **Increasing annular swirl:** improved mixing & creation of recirculation zones.
- **Increasing pressure:** faster chemistry & reduced ratio between bulk velocities and laminar flame speed.

How can we generalize a stability map to all parameters?

Comparison of time scales

 Comparison of **hydrodynamic** and **chemical** time scales.

- Hydrodynamic time scale:

$$\tau_t^{S2} = \frac{e}{\|\vec{u}_1 - \vec{u}_2\|}$$

- Chemical time scale:

$$\delta_l^0 / S_l^0$$

δ_l^0 a thermal thickness.

S_l^0 the unstretched laminar flame speed.

Here computed using GRI-Mech 3.0 mechanism [7].

Stability map

➤ Comparing $\tau_t^{S_2}$ with δ_l^0/S_l^0 makes it possible to identify stability zones of oxy-flames.

5. Conclusion & Future Work

Conclusion

- **New High Pressure test rig: OXYTEC HP combustor.**
- **Higher pressure reduces the flame-front length and promotes soot formation.**
- **Higher annular swirl intensity and momentum flux ratio favor the development of a recirculation zone.**
- **Increasing the CO₂ dilution reduces soot formation and increases flame-front length.**
- **Stability map comparing characteristic hydrodynamic and chemical timescales.**

Future Work

- To investigate a **wider variety of flame topologies** and further **complete the stability map**, extension of:
 - **Combustion and flow parameters.**
 - **Injector geometry:** use of **internal swirlers** and **different central pipe diameters.**
- **Measure the composition of burnt gases.**
- **Further investigate the impact of pressure on flame topology.**

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Thanks for your attention!

*This work is part of the **OXY3C** project of PEPR SPLEEN and was supported by the French National Research Agency, as a part of the France 2030 program, under grant **22-PESP-0009**.*